

VARIATION OF ABSOLUTE VISCOSITY WITH CONCENTRATION.
ORGANIC SOLUTE IN NON-AQUEOUS SOLVENT

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The viscosity of non-electrolytes in non-aqueous solvent has been studied at different concentrations. It has been shown that Taimini's second equation, $\ln \eta = \theta c + \phi$ is more applicable to these systems than the first equation, $\eta = mc + n$. The values of the constants, θ and ϕ , of the second equation have been calculated.

A number of equations relating viscosity with concentration has been proposed from time to time. Out of these expressions the equation of Arrhenius

$$\frac{\eta_s}{\eta_o} = A^c \text{ or } \ln \frac{\eta_s}{\eta_o} = c \ln A \text{ or } kc$$

has been found to be most useful. This equation has been studied by Rehyer (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1882, 2, 744), Wagner (*ibid.*, 1891, 5, 31) and others. They found that the equation was applicable within 1% up to 1N solutions in a number of cases. But Taimini and others have shown that the equation of Arrhenius is not applicable to the more concentrated solutions. Taimini (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1928, 32, 604; 1929, 33, 56) proposed two equations

$$\eta = mc + n \quad \dots (1)$$

$$\ln \eta = \theta c + \phi \quad \dots (2)$$

He has applied these to the supersaturated solutions investigated by him. The second equation of Taimini can be shown to be equivalent to the equation of Arrhenius as given below :

$$\ln \frac{\eta_s}{\eta_o} = kc$$

$$\text{or } \ln \eta_s - \ln \eta_o = kc$$

$$\text{or } \ln \eta_s = kc + \ln \eta_o$$

Now $\log \eta_o$ is a constant, say ϕ , at the constant temperature and for the same particular solvent. Hence

$$\ln \eta_s = \theta c + \phi.$$

In this paper an attempt has been made to ascertain if the above equations of Taimini are also applicable to the concentrated and supersaturated solutions of non-electrolytes in non-aqueous solvents.

EXPERIMENTAL

The method employed was that of Chatterji and Ram Gopal (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 24, 279) which essentially was the modified form of Scarpa's method. The viscosity was determined at five different concentrations and at various temperatures. For brevity of space the observations at only two different temperatures, lowest and highest, are recorded below. The concentrations are given in grams of anhydrous solute in 100 grams of pure solvent.

TABLE I

Viscosity and concentration

Solvent	Solute	Temp.	Viscosity at different concentrations				
			$c =$	15.66	20.00	25.50	32.00
Hexane	Naphthalene	30°	0.003636	0.003813	0.003926	0.004135	...
		45°	0.003166	0.003268	0.003406	0.003567	0.003785
	Diphenyl-amine	$c =$	7.20	9.83	12.50	33.33	86.85
		30°	0.003520	0.003675	0.003824	0.005085	0.015300
		45°	0.003079	0.003164	0.003288	0.004182	0.007796
		$c =$	54.00	59.00	82.00	92.00	118.00
Benzene	Naphthalene	30°	0.008077	0.008211	0.008740	0.009452	...
		45°	0.006540	0.006660	0.007066	0.007546	0.008170
	p-Dibromo-benzene	$c =$	66.40	75.60	90.80	112.80	138.00
		30°	0.007506	0.007715	0.008051	0.008631	...
		40°	0.006593	0.006739	0.007021	0.007521	0.008016
		$c =$	21.20	35.10	49.20	66.60	85.20
m-Dinitro-benzene	30°	0.006997	0.008048	0.009130	0.010540	...	
	45°	0.005698	0.006477	0.007265	0.008286	0.009624	
	$c =$	9.648	11.73	14.48	18.34	21.96	
	Benzoic acid	35°	0.005991	0.006160	0.006421	0.006626	...
45°		0.005267	0.005401	0.005600	0.005832	0.006100	
Toluene	Naphthalene	40°	0.007058	0.007571	0.007946	...	...
		50°	0.006270	0.006720	0.007058	0.007534	0.008217
	Acenaph-thene	$c =$	24.50	28.00	33.50	40.00	47.00
		30°	0.006888	0.007125	0.007479	0.007940	...
		45°	0.005730	0.005931	0.006035	0.006516	0.006900
		$c =$	182.50	280.00	487.00	830.00	...
o-Nitro-phenol	40°	0.018800	0.013430	0.016720	0.020160	...	
	50°	0.009420	0.011360	0.014110	0.016740	...	
CCl ₄	Naphthalene	40°	$c =$ 28.00	45.97	56.45	75.00	...
		50°	0.009335	0.010450	0.011090	...	...
	Acenaph-thene	$c =$	0.008138	0.009072	0.009672	0.009974	...
		$c =$	24.20	27.00	30.50	34.00	39.00
		25°	0.008920	0.009020	0.009340	0.009695	...
		40°	0.007199	0.007426	0.007610	0.007968	0.008631
m-Dinitro-benzene	25°	$c =$ 28.52	33.32	40.80	49.26	56.60	
	40°	0.010280	0.012080	0.012230	...	...	
	Chloro-benzene	45°	0.008356	0.008885	0.009900	0.011320	0.012130
		55°	$c =$ 62.00	76.00	90.00	112.00	136.00

TABLE I (contd.)

Solvent.	Solute.	Temp.	Viscosity at different concentrations				
			$c =$				
Bromo- benzene	<i>m</i> -Dinitro- benzene	35°	19.40	32.60	39.40	49.30	54.40
		45°	0.012210 0.010740	0.013910 0.012130	0.015510 0.013430	0.017220 0.014720	... 0.015760
..	<i>o</i> -Nitro- phenol	30°	134.00	187.00	332.00	535.00	...
		50°	0.018840 0.013500	0.021340 0.014770	0.026400 0.017730	... 0.019340	
Aniline	Naphthalene	35°	36.40	45.80	60.00	84.00	108.00
		55°	0.023650 0.015300	0.022910 0.015000	0.022240 0.014750	... 0.014330	... 0.014170
Acetone	Naphthalene	30°	44.83	56.00	68.00	84.00	100.00
		40°	0.004640 0.004207	0.004914 0.004423	0.005296 0.004781	0.005790 0.005170	0.006285 0.005571
Acetone	<i>o</i> -Nitro- aniline	25°	117.00	159.00	174.00	230.00	280.00
		40°	0.012290 0.009826	0.015150 0.012020	0.017420 0.013520	0.022570 0.017210	0.023660 0.018170
Methyl alcohol	Acet- anilide	30°	41.05	47.04	53.84	64.00	75.60
		40°	0.009180 0.007805	0.009842 0.008320	0.010570 0.008860	0.011590 0.009662	... 0.011660
..	Benzoic acid	30°	68.00	74.00	83.00	93.00	...
		45°	0.011960 0.009466	0.012900 0.010020	0.013600 0.010530	... 0.011330	
..	Urea	30°	20.00	22.00	24.00	27.00	30.00
		45°	0.008914 0.006933	0.009540 0.007466	0.009945 0.007656	0.010440 0.008155	0.011110 0.008588
Propyl alcohol	Benzoic acid	30°	40.00	44.00	50.00	56.00	...
		45°	0.025310 0.017700	0.026030 0.018160	0.027340 0.018810	0.028440 0.019650	
<i>iso</i> Propyl alcohol	<i>p</i> -Dibromo- benzene	30°	8.00	11.52	14.96	18.00	...
		45°	0.017130 0.011610	0.016630 0.011420	0.016770 0.011500	0.016820 0.011600	
<i>n</i> -Butyl alcohol	Naphthalene	40°	12.00	14.95	18.23	23.00	29.00
		50°	0.016700 0.013300	0.016330 0.013120	0.016240 0.013000	0.016010 0.012800	0.015670 0.012600
Acetic acid	Naphthalene	40°	15.51	20.91	28.00	36.00	48.00
		55°	0.010100 0.008163	0.010230 0.008190	0.010240 0.008243	0.010490 0.008373	... 0.008481

DISCUSSION

From the results given above the following types of curves have been plotted :
 (a) viscosity against concentration, (b) log viscosity against concentration. Of these two types of curves, log viscosity against concentration gives a more general and

clearer approach to linearity, hence only a few of these curves are given as typical examples. The plotted curves can be divided into three categories viz., (i) those which

FIG. 1

I. Benzene-*p*-dibromobenzene.
III. Chlorobenzene-naphthalene.

FIG. 2

II. CHCl_3 -acenaphthene.

give a straight line, (ii) those giving a curve with positive curvature, and (iii) those giving a negative curvature. Results are given in Table II.

TABLE II

Results of plot of log viscosity against concentration

Straight line.		Curve with a positive curvature.		Curve with a negative curvature.	
Solvent.	Solute.	Solvent.	Solute.	Solvent.	Solute.
1. Hexane	Naphthalene	Acetic acid	Naphthalene	Chlorobenzene	Naphthalene
2. „	Diphenylamine	Chloroform	Acenaphthene	Toluene	<i>o</i> -Nitrophenol
3. Benzene	Naphthalene	„	<i>m</i> -Dinitrobenzene	Bromobenzene	<i>o</i> -Nitrophenol
4. „	<i>p</i> -Dibromobenzene	Aniline	Naphthalene	Acetone	<i>o</i> -Nitrosaniline
5. „	<i>m</i> -Dinitrobenzene				
6. „	Benzoic acid				
7. Toluene	Naphthalene				
8. „	Acenaphthene				
9. CCl_4	Naphthalene				
10. Bromobenzene	<i>m</i> -Dinitrobenzene				
11. Acetone	Naphthalene				
12. MeOH	Acetanilide				
13. „	Benzoic acid				
14. „	Urea				
15. Propyl alcohol	Benzoic acid				

From the results recorded above it is found that the second equation of Taimini is generally obeyed by most of these solutions. At low temperatures there is a little curvature in some cases but at high temperature the curvature almost disappears and the curve merges into a straight line. If we consider two concentrations c_1 and c_2 , then the above equation becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \ln \eta_1 &= \theta c_1 + \phi \\ \text{and } \ln \eta_2 &= \theta c_2 + \phi \\ \text{or } \theta &= \frac{\ln \eta_2 - \ln \eta_1}{c_2 - c_1} \end{aligned}$$

i.e. ' θ ' denotes the change in viscosity per gram of solute. From the value of θ , which depends on the degree of solvation, a rough idea of relative solvation of different substances can be obtained. The greater the value of θ , higher is the solvation. Now, if in the above equation of Taimini, the concentration of the solute is taken to be zero, then we get

$$\ln \eta = \phi$$

i.e. ' η ' of pure solvent can be obtained.

The values of θ and ϕ have been calculated for the solutions which give a straight line plot for $\ln \eta = \theta c + \phi$. The results for θ and ϕ are given in Table III.

TABLE III

Solvent.	Solute.	Temp.	θ .	ϕ .	η (calc.)
1. Hexane	Naphthalene	45°	3.09×10^{-4}	3.4524	0.002834
2. „	Diphenylamine	45°	6.18	3.4379	0.002759
3. Benzene	Naphthalene	45°	1.58	3.7303	0.005374
4. „	<i>p</i> -Dibromobenzene	40°	1.17	3.7400	0.005495
5. „	<i>m</i> -Dinitrobenzene	45°	3.56	3.6868	0.004862
6. „	Benzoic acid	45°	5.19	3.6718	0.004696
7. Toluene	Naphthalene	45°	1.96	3.6923	0.004910
8. „	Acenaphthene	45°	4.31	3.6523	0.004490
9. CCl ₄	Naphthalene	50°	2.62	3.8181	0.006580
10. Bromobenzene	<i>m</i> -Dinitrobenzene	45°	4.84	3.9362	0.008650
11. Aniline	Naphthalene	55°	9.04×10^{-4}	2.1878	0.015410
12. Acetone	Naphthalene	40°	1.94×10^{-3}	3.5366	0.003440
13. MeOH	Acetanilide	40°	4.62 „	3.7032	0.005050
14. „	Benzoic acid	45°	4.10 „	3.6974	0.004982
15. „	Urea	45°	1.60×10^{-3}	3.5189	0.003303
16. Propyl alcohol	Benzoic acid	45°	2.77×10^{-3}	2.1371	0.013710
17. <i>iso</i> Propyl alcohol	<i>p</i> -Dibromobenzene	45°	1.13 „	2.0775	0.011960
18. <i>n</i> -Butyl alcohol	Naphthalene	50°	1.30 „	2.1374	0.013720

C O N C L U S I O N

From the results given above it is found that

1. For the solutions of toluene-naphthalene, carbon tetrachloride-naphthalene, benzene-benzoic acid and aniline-naphthalene the experimental and the calculated values of viscosity differ within 1%.

2. For the solutions of benzene-*m*-dinitrobenzene, isopropyl alcohol-*p*-dibromobenzene and butyl alcohol-naphthalene the difference between the calculated and the experimental value of viscosity is between 2% and 3%.

3. For the solutions of hexane-naphthalene, hexane-diphenylamine, benzene-naphthalene, toluene-naphthalene, methyl alcohol-acetanilide, and acetic acid-naphthalene the difference between the calculated and the experimental value of viscosity is between 5% and 10%.

4. For the solutions of acetone-naphthalene, methyl alcohol-urea, and methyl alcohol-benzoic acid the difference between the calculated and the experimental value of viscosity is above 10%.

In cases (1) and (2) the difference between the calculated and the experimental value of viscosity is much less than that in cases (3) and (4). It is probably due to the solvation being more marked in cases (3) and (4) than in cases (1) and (2).

The author wishes to express his thanks to Dr. A. C. Chatterji for guidance and to the Lucknow University for the facilities given in carrying out this investigation.

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
THE UNIVERSITY,
LUCKNOW.

Received August 4, 1947.